

PONTIFÍCIA UNIVERSIDADE CATÓLICA DO PARANÁ

ALEXSANDER CORDEIRO LOPES

**THE ROLE OF SELF-COMPASSION IN COPING WITH BURNOUT AND STRESS
AMONG RELIGIOUS LEADERS AND CLERGY: A SCOPING REVIEW
PROTOCOL**

CURITIBA

2025

ALEXSANDER CORDEIRO LOPES

**THE ROLE OF SELF-COMPASSION IN COPING WITH BURNOUT AND STRESS
AMONG RELIGIOUS LEADERS AND CLERGY: A SCOPING REVIEW
PROTOCOL**

Protocol for Reviewing the Scoping of Literature on the specific topic, presented to the Graduate Program in Theology at PUC-PR in preparation for writing a scientific article.

Doctoral advisor: Prof. Dr. Mary Rute Gomes Esperandio

CURITIBA

2025

1. ABSTRACT FOR THE PROTOCOL

Title of the Protocol:

The Role of Self-Compassion in Coping with Burnout and Stress among Religious Leaders and Clergy: A Scoping Review Protocol

Description/Abstract:

Introduction: Religious leaders and clergy represent a high-risk population for burnout syndrome and occupational stress, with alarming data pointing to serious consequences for their mental health. Self-compassion emerges as a key psychological construct for promoting resilience and well-being in this group. However, the literature on this specific relationship is dispersed across different disciplines, lacking a comprehensive overview.

Objective: This scoping review aims to map the extent and characteristics of the existing literature on the relationship between self-compassion and the coping with burnout syndrome and stress in religious leaders and clergy.

Methods: This scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews. A comprehensive search strategy will be applied to both published and unpublished literature. The following databases will be searched: PsycINFO, Scopus, PubMed, CINAHL, SciELO, LILACS, ATLA Religion Database, Web of Science, and ERIC, in addition to grey literature sources. Study selection and data extraction will be performed independently by two reviewers. Data will be analyzed and synthesized narratively and presented in diagrammatic and tabular forms, aligned with the review's objectives.

Expected Results: This review will map the available evidence, identify key concepts and definitions, and clarify the types of interventions and outcome measures used in this field. The findings will highlight knowledge gaps and inform the design of future primary studies and systematic reviews on effective interventions for this population.

Keywords: Self-Compassion; Burnout, Professional; Occupational Stress; Clergy; Religious Leaders; Mental Health; Scoping Review.

2. FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM AND RESEARCH QUESTION

1.1 Justification

Recently, the Vatican website "VaticanNews" published a concerning article titled "The suicide of priests in Brazil,"¹ written by subject matter expert Father Lício de Araújo Vale of the Diocese of São Miguel Paulista. His report states that from August 2016 to June 2023, forty priests died by suicide in Brazil—an average of about four per year.

While these numbers may seem low when considered proportionally to the total number of suicides in the general population², the issue at hand cannot be reduced to statistics alone. We must ask: What leads someone who has chosen to dedicate their life to caring for and nurturing meaning in the lives of others, to lose meaning in their own life?

Recent research has highlighted the growing problem of burnout among religious leaders. Burnout syndrome increasingly affects those serving in ministerial roles—including priests, pastors, and other religious figures—whether in a professional or voluntary capacity.³

Pastors experience burnout when their sense of vocation erodes into disillusionment; they often feel their work is never complete and question whether their efforts make a difference (Doolittle, 2008). Clergy members struggling with burnout report feelings of self-doubt, inadequacy, and exhaustion (Stanton-Rich & Iso-Ahola, 1998).⁴

According to Sanagiotto (2023)⁵, there is little empirical research on this topic in Brazil, signaling a need for further study. Still, based on the limited evidence available,

¹ VALE, Lício de Araújo. O suicídio de padres no Brasil. VaticanNews, 27 de jul. 2023. Available at: <<https://www.vaticannews.va/pt/igreja/news/2023-07/padre-licio-suicido-padres-brasil.html>>. Access em: 05 de out. 2024.

² According to the "Anuário Brasileiro de Segurança Pública" (Brazilian Public Security Yearbook), 16.025 took their own lives in our country in 2023 alone. That is 7.9 cases per 100,000 inhabitants. (ANUÁRIO BRASILEIRO DE SEGURANÇA PÚBLICA 2024. São Paulo: Fórum Brasileiro de Segurança Pública, year 18, 2024. ISSN 1983-7364.)

³ VIRGINIA, S. Burnout and depression among roman catholic secular, religious, and monastic clergy. Pastoral Psychology, V. 47, n. 1, p. 49-67, 1998 / RAJ, A; DEAN, K. Burnout and depression among catholic priests in India. Pastoral Psychology, 54, n.2, p. 157-171, 2005. / CREA, G. Correlati psicologici e motivazionali in un caso specifico di burnout professionale: il burnout tra preti e suore. Rassegna di Psicologia, v. 55, n. 2 p. 61-75, 2018 *apud* SANAGIOTTO, Vagner. Padres exaustos: a síndrome de burnout no contexto eclesial brasileiro. Petropolis, RJ Vozes, 2023, p 53.

⁴ BARNARD, L.; CURRY, J. The relationship of clergy burnout to self-compassion and other personality dimensions. Pastoral Psychology, v. 61, 2012. p 150. (Tradução nossa)

⁵ SANAGIOTTO, Vagner. Padres exaustos: a síndrome de burnout no contexto eclesial brasileiro. Petropolis, RJ Vozes, 2023, p 65.

it is clear that this is a real and urgent issue—one that demands academic, pastoral, theological, and professional mental health attention.

The problem of burnout within the Brazilian ecclesiastical context was further illustrated by a study conducted by the International Stress Management Association (ISMA-BR). Using a sample of 1,600 professionals in so-called "helping professions," the study found that priests and consecrated religious members were the most affected by burnout syndrome: 25% reported physical exhaustion, compared to 23% of police officers and 21% of corporate executives.⁶

These clear gaps in the literature justify the present scoping review, which seeks to map the existing knowledge and identify major theoretical and empirical gaps concerning this topic.

1.2 Formulation of the guiding question for the research

To formulate the key question for this scoping review, the **PCC framework** was used:

- **P - Population:** Religious leaders, clergy, pastors, and priests.
- **C - Concept:** The role of self-compassion.
- **C - Context:** The experience of stress and burnout syndrome within ministerial work.

Therefore, the central research question of this scoping review is: **What is currently known about the relationship between self-compassion and Burnout Syndrome and/or signs of stress in religious leaders and clergy?**

The resulting article from this review will be titled: **"Scope and characteristics of the existing literature on the relationship of self-compassion in overcoming burnout syndrome and signs of stress in religious leaders and clergy – a scoping review."**

1.3 Objective

To map the extent and characteristics of the existing literature on the relationship between self-compassion and burnout syndrome and/or signs of stress in religious leaders and clergy.

⁶ SANAGIOTTO, Vagner. Padres exaustos: a síndrome de burnout no contexto eclesial brasileiro. Petropolis, RJ Vozes, 2023, p 56.

3. WHY A SCOPING REVIEW?

A scoping review methodology was selected because it aims to map and describe the scope, range, and nature of existing literature, thereby identifying key concepts, types of evidence, and knowledge gaps. This approach is particularly useful in emerging or complex fields, or those characterized by diverse study designs. It is also valuable for generating hypotheses and informing the design of future systematic reviews.

Within this framework, the review seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- a) To explore and map the entire body of knowledge on the proposed topic, identifying which areas have been researched and, crucially, which areas remain unaddressed (i.e., the gaps).
- b) To delineate the boundaries of the existing literature on the subject by examining how far the research has progressed, which populations have been studied, which methodologies have been employed, and which concepts are being applied.

In summary, a scoping review is broad and exploratory, focused on identifying what is already known about the topic. It serves to map the entire landscape of a body of literature without the need to synthesize findings from every individual study in detail—as would be required in an Integrative or Systematic Review.

For the present study, the methodology will follow the guidelines proposed by the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) manual for scoping reviews. The reporting will adhere to the PRISMA-ScR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews) guidelines. The study protocol will be registered and made publicly available on the Zenodo platform and will be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

4. ESTABLISHMENT OF ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Inclusion Criteria:

- Timeframe: Last 20 years.
- Languages: Portuguese, English, Spanish, and Italian.

- Study Types: Randomized clinical trials (RCTs), quasi-experimental studies, cohort studies, and qualitative studies. Gray literature (theses and dissertations) will also be included.
- Population: Individuals from the Western world (primarily the Americas and Europe).
- Availability: Full text must be accessible.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Duplicate publications.
- Studies not focusing on religious leaders or clergy.
- Opinion pieces, editorials, and literature reviews.
- Articles for which only the abstract is available.

5. DATABASES

Access to the main databases will be provided primarily through the **CAPES Periodicals Portal** via the institutional subscription of *Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Paraná* (PUC-PR).

The following databases will be searched:

Database	Common Platform	Main Focus	Path to access
1. PsycINFO	EBSCOhost / APA	Psychology, Mental Health, Self-Compassion	CAPES
2. Scopus	Elsevier	Multidisciplinary (Scope)	CAPES
3. PubMed/MEDLINE	NIH	Biomedicine, Occupational Health, Burnout	Direct
4. CINAHL	EBSCOhost	Helping and Care Professions	CAPES
5. SciELO / LILACS	Direct	Latin American Literature	Direct
6. ATLA Religion Database	EBSCOhost	Religious Studies and Theology	Direct
7. Web of Science	Clarivate	Multidisciplinary (Scopus Alternative)	CAPES
8. ERIC	EBSCOhost	Educational Aspects of Leadership	CAPES
9. Gray Literature	Google Scholar	Theses and Dissertations	Direct

1.4 Initial Strategy for the PubMed Database

The following is a draft of the search strategy developed for the PubMed database, using all synonyms and Boolean operators:

("Clergy"[Mesh] OR (clerg*[tw] OR rabbi*[tw] OR priest*[tw] OR imam*[tw] OR deacon*[tw] OR chaplain*[tw] OR cleric*[tw] OR minister*[tw] OR pastor*[tw] OR "religious leader*[tw] OR "spiritual leader*[tw])) AND ("Burnout, Professional"[Mesh] OR (burnout[tw] OR "professional burnout"[tw] OR "occupational burnout"[tw] OR "career burnout"[tw] OR "job burnout"[tw] OR "emotional exhaustion"[tw] OR "work stress"[tw] OR "occupational stress"[tw] OR "job stress"[tw])) AND ("Self-Compassion"[Mesh] OR ("self-compassion"[tw] OR "self compassion"[tw] OR "self-kindness"[tw] OR "self kindness"[tw] OR "common humanity"[tw] OR "self-criticism"[tw] OR "self criticism"[tw] OR "mindful self-compassion"[tw] OR "MSC"[tw]))

Of course, it will be necessary to adapt to the particular syntax of each database, using controlled terms such as MeSH, Emtree, among others.

6. STUDY SELECTION PROCESS

Study screening will be conducted using the Rayyan platform. Reference management will be performed using the Mendeley reference manager under PUCPR's institutional subscription.

The study selection will involve two independent reviewers who will assess the titles/abstracts, followed by the full texts of potentially eligible studies.

The study selection flow will be documented using a PRISMA-ScR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews) flow diagram.

7. EXTRAÇÃO DE DADOS

For this scoping review, data from the included studies will be extracted using a standardized form developed specifically for this purpose. The following variables will be extracted, when applicable:

- **Bibliographic details:** authors, year of publication, country of origin, journal.
- **Study characteristics:** objectives, study design, methodology, follow-up duration.
- **Population characteristics:** religious denomination, ecclesiastical role, sample size, and eligibility criteria.
- **Concept details:** definitions and measurement instruments used for the concepts of self-compassion, stress, and burnout.

- **Main findings:** results and conclusions relevant to the research question of this scoping review.

Data extraction will be performed independently by two reviewers to ensure the reliability of the process.

8. PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The extracted data will be analyzed and synthesized based on the objectives of this scoping review. The analysis will follow a mixed approach, as detailed below:

Quantitative Analysis: A descriptive analysis of the data will be performed, using tables, graphs, and other visual aids to summarize the main characteristics of the included literature. This analysis will include, but is not limited to:

- Temporal and geographical distribution of studies (e.g., number of publications per year and country).
- Frequency of study designs and research methodologies used.
- General characteristics of the populations studied.

Qualitative Analysis: A narrative synthesis of the data will be conducted with the following objectives:

- Describe how key concepts (self-compassion, burnout, stress) are defined and operationalized in the studies.
- Identify central themes and patterns that emerge from the main findings.
- Map the progression and trends in knowledge over time.
- Discuss the evidence gaps identified in the literature.

9. BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- Brazilian Public Security Forum. (2024). *Brazilian yearbook of public security 2024*. Fórum Brasileiro de Segurança Pública.
- Barnard, L. K., & Curry, J. F. (2012). *The relationship of clergy burnout to self-compassion and other personality dimensions*. *Pastoral Psychology*, 61, p. 149-163.
- Sanagiotto, V. (2023). *Padres exaustos: A síndrome de burnout no contexto eclesial brasileiro* [Exhausted priests: Burnout syndrome in the Brazilian ecclesiastical context]. *Vozes*.
- Santos, C. M. C., Pimenta, C. A. M., & Nobre, M. R. C. (2007). A estratégia PICO para a construção da pergunta de pesquisa e busca de evidências [The PICO strategy for building the research question and searching for evidence]. **Revista Latino-Americana de Enfermagem*, 15*(3), 508–511. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0104-11692007000300023>
- Vale, L. A. (2023, July 27). O suicídio de padres no Brasil [The suicide of priests in Brazil]. *Vatican News*. <https://www.vaticannews.va/pt/igreja/news/2023-07/padre-licio-suicidio-padres-brasil.html>